

Hundred and eighty precepts of Lord Lao

By Johan Rols, EPHE

Entry tags: Lord Lao, Daoist Traditions, Religious Group, Precepts, Literary Chinese, Text, Language, Classical-Middle-Modern Sinitic, Revealed Text, Great Peace, Sino-Tibetan, Chinese Religion, Sinitic

The "Hundred and eighty precepts of Lord Lao" (Laojun bai bashi jie 老君百八十戒) is one of the earliest lists of Taoist precepts dating from the 4th - 6th century. The precepts deal with various themes relating to community life, in which social relationships, living beings, material things and the natural environment are all part of the same coherent whole to be respected. A third of the subjects mentioned, such as theft, murder or debauchery, are similar to the rules of Hinayanist Buddhist disciplines (Prātimokṣa). These Taoist precepts are moral exercises aimed at individual or collective salvation as well as self-transcendence. Their intoned recitation (songjie 誦戒) is incantatory psalmody and enables adepts to protect themselves from misfortune, wild beasts, and demons. Two versions of the "Hundred and eighty precepts of Lord Lao" appear in the 6th-century Taishang Laojun jinglü 太上老君經律 (DZ 786, 2a-20b) and the 8th-century Yaoxiu keyi jielü chao 要修科儀戒律鈔 (DZ 463, 14a-19a). There are also two variants of the Taishang Laojun jinglü text in the Yunji qiqian 雲笈七籤 (DZ 1032, 1a-14b) dating from the 11th century, and in two Dunhuang manuscripts from the Paul Pelliot collection preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (P. 4731 and P. 4562) which contain only the preface to the text and which is authenticated as dating from the 7th century. Part of the text and preface date from the 4th century, and the second part from the 6th century. According to the preface in the Taishang Laojun jinglü and its two variants, this list of precepts would be an appendix to the Taiping jing 太平經 revealed by deified Laozi (Lord Lao, Laojun) during the Eastern Zhou dynasty (8th - 3rd c. BCE) to a recipient named Gan Ji 干吉 (or Yu Ji 于吉). The site of the revelation is said to have been Langye 琅邪 in present day Shandong region.

Date Range: 300 CE - 500 CE

Region: Shandong

Region tags: China, Shandong

Shandong province

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Taishang Laojun jinglü 太上老君經律. In Zhengtong Daozang 正統道藏. 1988. Sanjiaben 三家本 collection. Shanghai: Shanghai shudian chubanshe, DZ 786, 2a-20b.
- Source 2: Yaoxiu keyi jielü chao 要修科儀戒律鈔. In Zhengtong Daozang 正統道藏. 1988. Sanjiaben 三家本 collection. Shanghai: Shanghai shudian chubanshe, DZ 463, 14a-19a.
- Source 3: Yunji qiqian 雲笈七籤. In Zhengtong Daozang 正統道藏. 1988. Sanjiaben 三家本 collection. Shanghai: Shanghai shudian chubanshe, DZ 1032, 1a-14b.

– Source 1: Pelliot 4731 and Pelliot 4562. In *Zhonghua Daozang* 中華道藏, 2003. Beijing: Huaxia chubanshe, t. 8, p. 595-596.

Notes: The "DZ" numbering above is based on the index of Taoist Canon texts by Kristofer Schipper and Chen Yaoting 陳耀庭: *Daozang suoyin* 道藏索引. 1996. Shanghai: Shanghai shudian chubanshe.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: [https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5c0183/000?](https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5c0183/000?query=%E8%80%81%E5%90%9B%E7%99%BE%E5%85%AB%E5%8D%81%E6%88%92#000-001a)

[query=%E8%80%81%E5%90%9B%E7%99%BE%E5%85%AB%E5%8D%81%E6%88%92#000-001a](https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5c0183/000?query=%E8%80%81%E5%90%9B%E7%99%BE%E5%85%AB%E5%8D%81%E6%88%92#000-001a)

– Source 1 Description: In *Taishang Laojun jinglü* 太上老君經律:

– Source 2 URL: [https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5b0147/005?](https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5b0147/005?query=%E8%80%81%E5%90%9B%E7%99%BE%E5%85%AB%E5%8D%81%E6%88%92#005-014a)

[query=%E8%80%81%E5%90%9B%E7%99%BE%E5%85%AB%E5%8D%81%E6%88%92#005-014a](https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5b0147/005?query=%E8%80%81%E5%90%9B%E7%99%BE%E5%85%AB%E5%8D%81%E6%88%92#005-014a)

– Source 2 Description: In *Yaoxiu keyi jielü chao* 要修科儀戒律鈔:

– Source 3 URL: <https://archivesetmanuscrits.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cc121003h>;

<https://archivesetmanuscrits.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cc120832f>.

– Source 3 Description: Dunhuang Manuscripts P. 4731 and P. 4562 in French National Library website:

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: I don't know

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, because it concerns the versions and variants of the text printed in the Taoist Canon. We don't know the original text.

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

Notes: No about this text.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– I don't know

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– I don't know

↳ Present part-time?

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– I don't know

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

Notes: See the note of Taiping jing in Religiondatabase :
<https://religiondatabase.org/browse/1324>

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– I don't know

Notes: A revealed text should not normally be modified, since it is a particular revelation. Rather than modifying a text, new revealed texts resulting from interactions between Chinese gods and humans are produced frequently. However, the two versions of this text show that its content has in fact been modified. The original version is unknown.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– No

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– I don't know

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– I don't know

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– I don't know

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– I don't know

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– I don't know

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Prophet

– Divinity

– Institutions

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– I don't know

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– I don't know

- ↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?
 - I don't know

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

- Field doesn't know

Notes: This text may concern all priests and the Taoist community.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

- No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

- I don't know

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

- Yes

Notes: The moral practice of the precepts evoked in this text allows a purification of the priest which is necessary in ritual practices.

- ↳ Is it orally recited?

- Yes

Notes: It's a psamody

- ↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

- Yes

- ↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

- I don't know

- ↳ On the reciter?

- Yes

Notes: The recitation of the text is incantatory, protecting the follower from danger.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?
– I don't know

↳ Is it read?
– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?
– I don't know

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?
– I don't know

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
– Specify: Psalmody

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
– I don't know

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
– I don't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?
– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices?
– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?
– I don't know

- ↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?
 - I don't know

Is there material significance to the text?

- No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

- No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

- Yes

- ↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?
 - I don't know

- ↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?
 - Yes

Notes: There is some debate as to which of the two versions is closer to the original text.

- ↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?
 - Yes

Notes: The most readable version is used as the main reference (the Taishang Laojun Jinglü)

- ↳ Age of extant version of text?
 - Yes

- ↳ Content of text?
 - Yes

- ↳ Ritual purpose of text?
 - No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of a collection of texts about Taoist moral rules and precepts.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– I don't know

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– I don't know

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Precepts list

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: No, but it's possible that some of the topics covered in the legal texts are also present in the moral rules mentioned in this text.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– I don't know

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Some of the precepts mention how to behave during burials and certain places where graves

are forbidden.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– I don't know

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the preface : Lord Lao (Laozi) is an incarnation of the Dao, the principle that generates all that exists and the fundamental power that flows through all things in the universe. The list of precepts mentions only to the Great Dao, the gods and demons in general, without definitions and descriptions.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– I don't know

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– I don't know

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– I don't know

↳ Can be hurt?

– Yes

Notes: It's possible to harm it by upsetting the cosmic balance.

- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living
 - Yes

- ↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
 - I don't know

Previously human spirits are present

- I don't know

Non-human supernatural beings are present

- Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - I don't know

- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - I don't know

- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: I don't know

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
– I don't know

↳ Other organization of pantheon?
– Specify: I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Laozi (Human) / Laojun (divine being) in Dunhuang manuscripts

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?
– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?
– Yes

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?
– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
- ↳ In dreams?
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Through divination practices?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Only through religious specialists?
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch?
 - No
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: I don't know

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?
 - No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– Yes

↳ Food
– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Sacred object(s)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

↳ Incest

– No

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– Yes

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– Yes

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural being wants everyone to practice these precepts.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: animal life, objects, resources...

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

- ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other form of punishment
 - Specify: To go to the nine prisons of torments of the underworld.
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Consists of bad luck?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Political failure?
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Defeat in battle?
 - No
 - ↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
 - Yes

- ↳ Disaster on journeys?
 - Yes
- ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - No
- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - No
- ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - No
- ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - No
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - I don't know

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - I don't know
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other?
 - I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– I don't know

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text evokes divine punishments for those who fail to follow the precepts, but it does not explicitly evoke an apocalyptic end.

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– I don't know

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - Yes
 - Notes: It's more a question of maintaining cosmic balance of yin and yang.
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - Yes
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: I don't know
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ All members of the sample region will survive
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Other survival condition [specify]
 - Specify: to practice the precepts

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes

- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Monogamy (females)
– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)
– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)
– Yes

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: It is a practice of moral discipline that enables the adept to find salvation and transcend into an immortal or divine official.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Incense burning is mentioned, but no specific ritual name is given.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: National and local taoist communities

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– I don't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– Yes

Notes: Some precepts refer to the relationship between masters and disciples, but these are more concerned with the right attitude to have towards each other.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– I don't know

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, if we consider that precepts are the content of education

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: Not directly

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: Only the food taboos

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